

Abortion: Unimaginable Consequences and ‘Regret Medicine’

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Abstract

Abortion is a common practice worldwide, with an estimated 73 million induced cases annually. While its physical and psychological consequences are increasingly recognized in medical literature, most conventional studies neglect the deeper spiritual and karmic dimensions. These include the undiscovered effects on family members, future offspring, and even the medical professionals involved in the procedures. Drawing on the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and the teachings of Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu, this paper explores the perspective that the spirits of aborted, miscarried fetuses, or deceased fertilized embryos continue to exist. If not properly ascended, they may endure immense suffering and, in turn, cause suffering to others. We present 27 Dharma teachings and 5 real-life case studies demonstrating how sincere repentance, recitation of Buddhist scriptures, and life liberation can resolve karmic debts, help these spirits ascend, and restore physical, emotional, and familial well-being. Our findings suggest that unresolved spiritual matters are among the most significant contributors to various rare and intractable health conditions. This work advocates for a holistic understanding of the impacts of abortion, miscarriage, and embryonic loss on human health, offering a pathway to healing through Buddhist practice.

Keywords: Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door; Golden Buddhist Practices; Abortion; Deceased fertilized embryos; Spirits; Family harmony

Introduction

Each year, approximately 73 million induced abortions occur worldwide. Approximately 61% of all unintended pregnancies, and 29% of all pregnancies, end in induced abortion [1]. These numbers reveal that terminating life before birth has become a disturbingly common practice. But what are the consequences of this widespread phenomenon?

From a medical perspective, abortion can have significant adverse effects on women’s health, including mental health disorders [2,3], suicidal ideation [4], and a range of psychological and physical complications [5]. Some women also experience post-abortion syndrome, characterized by emotional distress, regret, and trauma [6,7].

However, most existing studies are limited in scope. They rarely explore the broader impact of abortion on other family members, such as living children, or on the doctors who perform the procedures.

Our previous reports suggest that the consequences of abortion extend far beyond what is commonly recognized. Abortion has been linked to a range of severe and often incurable illnesses in women, such as lung cancer [8], lumbar disc herniation [8], amyotrophic lateral sclerosis [8], insomnia [8], asthma [9], myasthenia gravis [10], syringomyelia [11], chronic idiopathic constipation [12], and rheumatoid arthritis [13]. It has also been associated with serious and lasting health issues in their living children or grandchildren, such as glutaric aciduria type I [14], severe depression [15], Oppositional defiant disorder (ODD) [16], parapsychoarchia (schizophrenia) [17], autism [18], Prader-Willi syndrome [19], drug addiction [20], facial paralysis [21], down syndrome [22], and epilepsy [23]. Alarmingly,

abortion may pose significant health risks even to the medical professionals who perform these procedures, including life-threatening conditions such as leukemia [8].

Abortion can lead to hundreds, or even thousands, of chronic and seemingly incurable conditions-findings we intend to publish progressively. Why does abortion result in such a wide range of illnesses? The root cause lies in the fact that, although the physical bodies of aborted babies perish, their souls continue to exist. Once separated from the body, these souls become 'ghosts'; however, we refer to them respectfully as 'spirits.' This concept has been explored in depth in our previous review [8].

Modern science largely overlooks this dimension, as the existence of spirits is typically viewed as a matter of religious belief rather than empirical fact. Since spiritual entities cannot be seen, touched, or measured, they fall outside the scope of conventional scientific inquiry. As a result, many post-abortion health issues remain difficult for doctors to treat, with interventions often targeting symptoms rather than underlying causes. In contrast, Buddhist practitioners, guided by Dharma teachings and without the need for extensive medical training, are frequently able to address these conditions at their karmic and spiritual root [8-23].

To deepen the understanding of how and why these baby spirits can profoundly affect the health of family members and even medical professionals, this paper presents 27 spiritual insights from Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu, along with 5 real-life cases that applied His Dharma teachings. We hope this paper will raise awareness among pregnant women and families planning to have children: Please do not abort your baby, or you may face lifelong regret. For those who have already experienced abortion or miscarriage, we also share Master Lu's guidance on how to sincerely repent and take Dharma action to ascend the spirits to transform this karmic burden into a healthier and more peaceful life.

Some terms or concepts discussed here may be unfamiliar to readers; we encourage you to consult our previous reports for further explanation [8, 17].

Consequences of Abortion

Q&A 1. Will the Spirits of Aborted Children be Activated Through the Recitation of Buddhist Scriptures [24]?

(This dialogue took place in the Penang Dharma conference in Malaysia on Jan. 22, 2015)

Inquirer: Will spirits of the aborted or miscarried children, like other spirits, also be activated by Buddhist scripture recitation?

Master Lu: In fact, the aborted child spirits generally remain attached to the mother. Even if you do not actively "activate" them through scripture recitation, they are already on the mother's body. That is why abortion is extremely harmful. These spirits were meant to be born into the human realm and had a designated place here. But after being killed before birth, they have no way to reincarnate and nowhere to go. A little spirit like that can only stay inside the mother's womb. "You killed me. My physical body

is gone, but my soul remains attached to you." That is why so many women suffer from serious gynecological problems. It is not that you are activating the spirit by reciting scriptures. It has been there all along.

I often tell you that when you are ascending your aborted children, the child will sometimes let you see them. That is because they have always been with you. They are also spirits who died unjustly, with nowhere to go. In Buddhism, it is said that no matter how hopeless one feels, suicide is never an option. If you take your own life, you will have nowhere to go and will end up in the City of Unjust Deaths in the underworld. They sometimes linger over graves, and sometimes wander into hospitals. If they find someone to take their place, they may be able to reincarnate. That is why you must avoid places where people often die. In Hong Kong, houses where someone has died (known as "yin residences") (阴宅) can drop in value by nearly half. Real estate listings may explicitly state if a house is a "yin residence." In contrast, a "yang residence" (where no one has died) (阳宅) will fetch a higher price.

You must understand this: when a child dies from abortion, they remain with the mother forever. The mother can never truly be happy. So, remember this well:

First, never have an abortion.

Second, if you have already had one, you must recite Buddhist scriptures to ascend them.

Q&A 2. A Mother Slandered Buddhism and Had an Abortion, Resulting in Gastric Cancer and Her Son with Autism [25]

(Totem Reading at the Paris Dharma Conference in France on October 1, 2017)

Inquirer: I will bear my own karmic obstacles; I will not let Master Lu bear them. My child, born in 2005, is 12 years old and was born in the Year of the Rooster. He does not speak.

Master: There is something wrong (with his brain).

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: I am telling you. This is autism.

Inquirer: That is right.

Master: He likes to stay in his room all day and talks to himself at night.

Inquirer: Exactly.

Master: There is a powerful foreign spirit on him. First, you had an abortion or miscarriage.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: That aborted child is now on his hands, which is why he keeps grabbing at you with both hands.

Inquirer: Yes, he even hits and kicks me.

Master: That is because you killed him. He possessed your son's body and used it to hit you. Secondly, there is killing karma

in your family. At night, your son starts talking to himself, his body jerks, and he even likes to crawl.

Inquirer: That is right.

Master: Because there is also an animal spirit on him. This animal spirit even goes up to your rooftop. Sometimes you can hear noises from up there. What is his name?

Inquirer: Ch- H- [phonetic].

Master: If you do not mind, I will ask him to behave. Ch- H-! Did you see that? He clapped.

Inquirer: Master, please save him.

Master: The spirit on him hates you deeply. It wants to drag you down. It is not just hitting you; it wants to seize you.

Inquirer: Yes, I am in a lot of pain.

Master: If you are in pain, you must recite Buddhist scriptures. You need to vow to adopt a full vegetarian diet.

Inquirer: I will.

Master: Not "will", you must vow now.

Inquirer: I vow right now.

Master: You must remember your vow. Otherwise, this child will not spare you and will drain your household finances. He was, in fact, quite normal for a while after birth. After that spirit suddenly possessed him...

Inquirer: Yes, he was normal up to about 18 months old.

Master: There is currently still a small animal on him, similar to a donkey. This comes from ancestral killing karma. An elder in your family once killed such an animal, and now it is on him. He tries to eat anything he sees.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: You need to recite 850 Little Houses for his karmic creditors.

Inquirer: Okay.

Master: Release about 3,000 fish, gradually.

Inquirer: My mother-in-law has already helped release over 1,000.

Master: That is not enough. You must continue.

Inquirer: Okay.

Master: His condition worsens at night. You must frequently recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* at night and pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva: "Guan Yin Bodhisattva, please have great compassion. I vow to recite 870 Little Houses for his karmic creditors."

Inquirer: I definitely will.

Master: You must say it clearly.

Inquirer: I will.

Master: Everyone, did you hear? A fellow practitioner from Canada shared earlier that her child used to hit her too, worse than this one. Tell everyone, are you suffering?

Inquirer: I am in great pain.

Master: I will ask the spirit to temporarily leave and make the child behave. You must recite well. Your family has heavy killing karma... [At this point, the child screams. Master Lu sternly stops him, and the child goes quiet.] See? Asking the spirit to leave is not easy. Let him squat. It is okay.

[To bodyguard:] Bodyguard, manage him, manage him.

Recite diligently. Learn Buddhism earnestly. You must change. Your speech karma is very heavy. When you were young, you said inappropriate things at temples.

Inquirer: Yes, before I got married, I was a believer in a certain Western religion. I did not believe in Buddhism at all.

Master: See?

Inquirer: I repent.

Master: Let me tell you, karma never fails. Practice sincerely. This is your retribution, clear and visible.

Inquirer: He still occasionally makes inappropriate gestures and wraps himself up like a zongzi (粽子) when sleeping.

Master: I know. He has not harmed you yet, but he will. He will do indecent things to you. Do you believe it?

Inquirer: I believe it.

Master: You believe it now, huh?

Inquirer: I do.

Master: Why didn't you believe earlier?

Inquirer: I had not yet come across Master Lu. I have only been learning for about a month...

Master: Saving someone who did not believe before?

Inquirer: I believe now.

Master: Recite diligently and go fully vegetarian. After reciting the Little House, the child will improve. He will be much better-behaved when you recite halfway through. This is not unusual.

Inquirer: Master Lu, could you also look at me? I was born in 1979, the Year of the Sheep. I have gastric cancer. How many Little Houses to recite and how many fish to release? The doctor called me last Friday, but I have not told my family yet.

Master: Make a vow quickly. Recite *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* five times daily. How old are you now?

Inquirer: 39.

Master: It is a predestined calamity. The ages of 369 are critical years [8]. A deceased old woman in your family is trying to drag you away (to the underworld). Recite diligently. Your own speech karma was too severe in the past.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Your gastric cancer is in the gastrointestinal area.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: It has already started to spread.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Truly! If you do not understand or do not believe, do not speak ill of others. You do not have to believe, but do not slander. Look at your child. He will destroy you. After he was born, your family's finances gradually declined. He came to collect a karmic debt.

Inquirer: That is right.

Master: Recite properly. It will not be easy. If you do not practice Buddhism appropriately, your life is in his hands.

Inquirer: I understand. How many Little Houses do I need?

Master: 540.

Inquirer: How many fish are to be released?

Master: 2,800.

Inquirer: Got it. Thank you, Master Lu.

Master: Do your best.

Inquirer: I will.

Master: These are your own karmic offenses. How can you speak recklessly?

Inquirer: I understand. I repent.

Master: There are currently two spirits on him. Do you often hear noises in your kitchen?

Inquirer: I feel something.

Master: Clanging and banging.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: That spirit often rummages through your fridge.

Inquirer: Yes, the fridge is malfunctioning.

Master: Age 39 is a major predestined calamity. Make great vows, or you will die. Sorry to say that.

Inquirer: How should I make great vows? Please enlighten me.

Master: First, eat a full vegetarian diet. Second, if you recover, testify and share your story like the other fellow Buddhist practitioners just did. Third, once you get a little better, go out to help others, be a volunteer.

Inquirer: I will.

Master: You are an extremely stingy person, and you do not treat your mother-in-law well.

Inquirer: Sometimes, when angry, I say harsh things.

Master: Even if she is not good, it does not excuse your behaviour, does it? Understand?

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Change your faults. You must change them. Once you finish reciting for the child's creditors, he will recover.

Inquirer: Thank you, Master Lu.

Master: Everyone, don't you think this is pitiful? If your child were like this, wouldn't you say it is tragic? The mother's biggest problem was not believing and her speech karma. If she had been better, just 100-200 Little Houses would have made the child stop hitting her. But she did not believe in the beginning.

Q&A 3. Miscarried Fetus Affects Gynecological Health If Not Ascended (Excerpt) [26]?

(This dialogue took place over the phone on July 22, 2014)

Caller: Master, I was born in 1983, the Year of the Pig. Could you check if I can still have children? Also, please look at my overall health condition.

Master: You have been pregnant before.

Caller: Yes, I have. But can I still have children?

Master: Your left fallopian tube is blocked.

Caller: I had a dream about this. I saw that my right fallopian tube was fine, but the left side looked a little dark. I did not understand why.

Master: It is very simple. First, the aborted child has not been ascended and often interferes with your gynecological health. This is what we call being affected by a spirit. Second, you have not been careful with your diet. Every person's physical condition is different, so food choices affect each person's health and nutritional balance differently.

(Some dialogue omitted here)

Caller: Master, can you check if the spirit of the miscarried child has left?

Master: Your digestive system is in poor condition. That child is still around, and it is serious. It is a boy.

Caller: How many Little Houses do I need to recite?

Master: Oh dear, he requires a lot: 69 sheets.

Caller: Okay, I will recite them.

Master: If you do not recite enough to ascend him, you will not be able to get pregnant.

Caller: I see. Master, can you check if I have any other spirits on me? Do I still need to recite for karmic creditors? I often dream about...

Master: Yes, you have one more karmic creditor.

Caller: How many Little Houses does this one need? I have already recited more than sixty sheets.

Master: Actually, you have two more. One only needs 13 sheets, and the other needs 27.

Caller: Understood. Master, can you also check if there are any spirits in my house?

Master: Yes. Your house has many small wandering spirits.

Caller: How many Little Houses are needed? I already recited 7 sheets before, and I have heard noises in the house.

Master: That is not enough. Recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 108 times a day for one month straight.

Caller: Okay. Master, could you sense the quality of my scripture recitations?

Master: They are okay. The quantity is too low, but the quality of your recitation is acceptable.

Caller: What about the quality of my Little Houses?

Master: Also, acceptable.

Caller: Master, one more thing, can you check my Buddhist altar?

Master: The altar is mainly affected by the spirits in your home. There are too many small spirits around, so lately Bodhisattva has not been coming.

Q&A 4. Birth Control Pills May Kill Many Embryos and Cause Gynecological Issues [27]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 18, 2014)

Caller: Hello, Master Lu! Please help check my condition. I was born in 1971, the Year of the Pig. I would like to know about my health and whether I have any spirits on me.

Master: The main issues are in your digestive system and gynecological area.

Caller: Yes, yes, that is right.

Master: These areas are very prone to growing tumors.

Caller: Oh... I also have trouble sleeping at night. I always wake up between 2 and 5 a.m.

Master: Waking up during that time is related to a spirit on you.

Caller: Oh...

Master: Oh, my goodness, there are so many of them.

Caller: Could it be my mother?

Master: No. There are many children.

Caller: Oh. I know I had one abortion. So far, I have recited over 400 Little Houses myself, and another 400 were recited by others, totalling 800. Please check how many more Little Houses I need.

Master: At least 300 more.

Caller: Okay.

Master: Right now, there are still many child spirits on you. I estimate at least 24.

Caller: What?!

Master: You must have used some form of birth control or taken medication back then.

Caller: Master Lu, you are absolutely right. I did take pills, yes!

Master: That explains it. Taking such medication means the embryos had already started forming. The drugs then killed them, essentially destroying the fertilized eggs. Because you were already pregnant or fertilized for the drug had to take effect, and those lives were ended. Now, you must recite Buddhist scriptures to help these spirits ascend. There is no other way. Otherwise, it will affect you. When many aborted child spirits remain on your body, they can (1) cause your lower back issues; (2) lead to bone aches all over your body.

Caller: I understand now. I really get it.

Q&A 5. Dream Revealed the Miscarriage Was a Molar Pregnancy-Only After Ascending the Fetus Can Conception Be Possible [28]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on March 9, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! I am in my second marriage and have been trying to conceive, but it has not happened. Last year, I thought I had a miscarriage... I began practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in August and have frequently dreamed of Master Lu. A few days ago, I dreamed I was on the phone with you, and you told me about the miscarriage with my current husband that was a molar pregnancy, and that I need to recite 1,300 Little Houses. I am really anxious.

Master: It is simple. If you recite all 1,300 Little Houses, there is a chance you can get pregnant. If you do not, you will not even have the opportunity. I have already told you this in your dream.

Caller: I also dreamed of you before. I asked whether I could still have children, and you gave me a white plastic ring and said, "You wear this until you conceive."

Master: If you finish reciting the 1,300 Little Houses, you will likely be able to have a child. Now it is up to you. Don't say anything else to me.

Caller: I will recite diligently. Are there any other spirits or karmic debts on me? Is it serious?

Master: It is manageable.

Caller: About how many child spirits are on me?

Master: Just the child spirits alone will need 28 Little Houses.

Caller: So, three child spirits?

Master: Yes. Altogether, recite 1,300. Start with 49 sheets. Then do 28, then 21, then another 21-keep going like that.

Caller: My current husband and his ex-wife aborted three children. Should I recite Little House for him, too?

Master: Absolutely.

Caller: Should I write “my name’s child” or “his name’s child” on the Little Houses?

Master: Write “his name’s child,” because the children are not yours.

Caller: Could you help me adjust my daily recitation routine? Currently, I recite: 49 times the *Great Compassion Mantra*, 21 times the *Heart Sutra*, 3 times the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, 108 times the *Cundi Dharani*, 49 times the *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou*, 108 times the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots*, and 27 times the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*.

Master: That is fine.

Q&A 6. In-Vitro Fertilization (IVF) equals abortion and killing [29]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Dec. 27, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! A fellow Buddhist practitioner had two abortions in the past. Five years into her marriage, she still could not conceive, so she underwent IVF. The first embryo transfer failed. After practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, she made vows, performed life liberation, and prayed for a child. During the second embryo transfer, one embryo implanted. However, on Day 24 and Day 34 of the transfer, ultrasounds showed no fetal heartbeat or fetal pole. The doctor diagnosed a fetal demise and recommended curettage. Master, may I ask why this fellow practitioner experienced a fetal death? Was it because the number of Little Houses recited was insufficient, or were her merits and virtues not enough?

Master: This kind of situation is very simple. She has already done IVF once. Do you know how many embryos die in the process? Every embryo is a spiritual being, a soul. How many Little Houses do you think she would need to recite to compensate? She has not even paid off her past karmic debts. How could good things happen to her?

Caller: Oh, then what should she do?

Master: She must repent thoroughly! There are many fetuses she knows about and many she does not. I do not want to say more. What is the use of looking beautiful? With such heavy karmic debts, how can she successfully give birth? There are things I can see, but I choose not to speak of them, because they are karmic issues, and they are very troublesome...

Q&A 7. Miscarried Fetal Spirits May Cause Tumors If They Remain for Too Long [30]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on March 23, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! How am I doing now? Could you take a look?

Master: You need to recite Buddhist scriptures diligently. I am telling you; something may grow in your body. You must recite more Little Houses. ...If you cannot sleep well at night, it means there are spirits in your body. Have you had abortions?

Caller: Yes, I have.

Master: Did you help them ascend?

Caller: I have been feeling unwell recently and have been reciting scriptures.

Master: How many Little Houses have you recited?

Caller: My younger sister has given me dozens. The children were addressed using my name on Little Houses.

Master: Hmm. I am telling you; they may not have left. I can see that you have had more than one abortion.

Caller: That is correct.

Master: See, and you even had your sister recite Little House for you! You must do it yourself. Let me tell you, if they have been there too long, they get impatient. When that happens, trouble arises. If you are diagnosed with a mass somewhere, you will be in trouble! You must continue reciting. If you do not, you are inviting cancer.

Q&A 8. A Grandmother Had Over Ten Abortions, and Her Grandson Was Born with Cerebral Palsy [31]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on March 16, 2014)

Caller: Hello, Master! A fellow Buddhist practitioner’s son, now ten months old, was diagnosed with cerebral palsy, though the MRI results were normal. Master Lu previously read his totem and prescribed 800 Little Houses and a large amount of life liberation. Later, the practitioner told me that her mother had at least ten abortions and used to be an Obstetrics and Gynecology (OB-GYN). Could this have directly caused her grandson’s cerebral palsy?

Master: This is a very simple question. Her mother is directly responsible.

Caller: She wants to know if the child, being only 10 months old, could still recover to normal by doing a large number of life liberations and reciting Little House.

Master: Recovery is definitely possible. If you use Dharma methods to heal, he will recover; if you use medical treatment, he will also recover. As long as there is effort, there will be recovery. To what extent he recovers—that’s another matter.

Caller: Since her mother had more than 10 abortions, how many Little Houses should be recited per aborted child?

Master: At least 21 Little Houses per child. I can see her mother’s appearance. She is quite good-looking.

Q&A 9. Previous Miscarriage Affects Current Fetus [32]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on December 27, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! I am currently pregnant, but in the past two days, I have dreamt of giving birth to a pair of boy-girl twins. What does that mean?

Master: Twins can indicate two possibilities. One, it could mean there are two spirits trying to reincarnate through this pregnancy,

both trying to enter your womb, which is why you dreamed of twins. Two, it could be your strong desire for either a boy or a girl, while your fate actually calls for the opposite gender. For example, if you are destined to have a girl but keep praying hard for a boy, such a wish can result in a dream of boy-girl twins. Lastly, there is also another possibility: the aborted child from your past.

Caller: Oh, I do remember miscarrying a child two months before this pregnancy.

Master: That is exactly it. Now you are in trouble. Two spirits are competing to come through you. It is like one was assigned by the King of Hell, and the other one, who was your aborted baby, is also trying to reincarnate. If born, this child may become a karmic debt collector.

Caller: Oh... So, when I recite Little Houses now, should I write "To my karmic creditor" or "To my child"?

Master: Of course, you should address it to your child! Quickly help your aborted baby ascend. If you do not, and both spirits try to enter the same body, it could endanger your life. One physical body with two spirits is like a form of mental illness: One being the primary spirit, the other constantly interfering and speaking to it. This is extremely dangerous. Isn't schizophrenia (parapsychoarchia) already difficult enough to deal with?

Q&A 10. Cause of Constant Quarreling Between Husband and Wife [33]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on May 31, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! I do not know why, but my spouse and I constantly argue. We fight over trivial, messy things...

Master: A couple's relationship is karmic, either a positive or negative bond. Without karma, there is no meeting; without karma, there is no repayment. Many couples are wonderful to each other before marriage, but after marriage, constant quarrels erupt. That is due to both good and bad karma surfacing.

Given your situation, the first thing to examine is whether either of you has had abortions or miscarriages. If so, the aborted child's spirit will not leave you. It will often possess you or your spouse, causing fights. It hates you both for killing it. It has no physical body, only a spiritual one. So, when it enters your body, you lose your temper easily.

If you often lose your temper for no reason, that is a sign of an aborted child's spiritual presence. You must act quickly to ascend it. Without timely ascending, the karmic entanglement will worsen. After repentance and reciting Little Houses, observe whether your relationship with your spouse improves.

Q&A 11. Miscarriage Causes Child to Cry and Misbehave [34]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Oct. 19, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! Why does my child cry all the time every day?

Master: Think about whether you have had any abortions or miscarriages. If you have, that is the cause. Recite 21 Little Houses for your aborted child.

Caller: Really? So, am I the one affecting my child?

Master: That is right! The aborted child's spirit is now attached to your living child. Make a vow to recite 49 Little Houses for ascending it. After you make the vow, watch if your child still cries at night. If the crying continues, recite the *Heart Sutra* for your child. If it happens after midnight, recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*. Do you have a Buddhist altar at home?

Caller: Yes, yes, I do!

Master: Then everything will be fine.

Q&A 12. Frequent Abortions in a Region May Lead to Famine [35]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Dec. 9, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! If a child dies either during pregnancy or at a very young age, why can't it reincarnate into the same family again in a future pregnancy?

Master: That's not possible. Once a child is aborted or dies young, it's extremely difficult for them to reincarnate again unless you recite Little Houses to help them. Without ascending, they usually descend to lower realms. It is a terrible situation. They have lost their blessings.

Caller: Do they become wandering spirits?

Master: Yes. That is why in villages or rural areas where many abortions occur, famine is more likely to happen. Many of these aborted children fall into the Hungry Ghost Realm. Places with high abortion rates tend to struggle with basic sustenance.

Caller: So, can frequent abortions bring disaster to the local area?

Master: Yes.

Caller: The root cause is the presence of these spirits?

Master: Exactly.

Q&A 13. Master Lu's Teachings: Answers to Letters of Inquiry (262) [36]

(Excerpt from Master Lu's Q&A (262), 31 October 2018)

Inquirer: On 30 September 2018, after paying respect to Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, the statue of Guan Yin Bodhisattva radiated brilliant light. Not long after, the Bodhisattva sent a thought to me: "I will take you to observe the scenes of hell so that the sentient beings of the Human Realm will understand the law of karma and refrain from performing filthy acts. Sexual desires breed evil. Nowadays, men and women are sinking so low in pursuit of lustful satisfaction, but in the future, they will descend into the Lower Realms. It will be too late for regrets then."

The Hell of Icy Coldness (The Hell of Snowy Mountains) and The Hell of Icy Coldness (The Hell of Icicles) (details omitted)

The Hell of Iron Mountains: Women who commit deeds of sexual misconduct and perform abortions, and men who act promiscuously or instigate women to perform abortions, will be punished here.

The environment in this Hell was very dark and overshadowed by many enormous iron mountains. I heard the distant cries of infants, and when I moved closer, what I found made me jump.

The sky was filled with a countless number of floating baby spirits, all full of resentment. You can tell that the practice of abortion is common in the Human Realm.

The mountains were covered in many iron trees, while on the ground awaited a cover of countless and minuscule iron spikes. Razor-sharp spikes also grew out of the iron trees. I saw an enforcement officer pursue a group of offenders who were being continually lashed with a whip as they were forced up the iron mountain. The offenders were all wailing as the bottoms of their blood-coloured feet were constantly and repeatedly pierced by the sharp spikes. Some offenders, overcome with the pain and no longer able to stand, tried to hold onto trees for support, but their hands were also bloodied and pierced by the sharp spikes that grew out of them. Every offender was forced up the mountain, one excruciating step at a time, only to be forced to traipse back down again. It was unbearable to watch.

The enforcement officers show no leniency. If the offenders stop moving, they are immediately lashed. So, they go up and come down the iron mountain over and over again until they have served the full term of their sentence. Only then may they leave this Hell.

Why is the punishment for abortion so severe, and especially for those who intend to abort their child? It's because the spirit of the baby has no other choice other than to occupy their mother's body after they are aborted. This leads to massive suffering for their parents, like gynaecological diseases, depression and shortened lifespan. When their mother dies, they each will go their separate ways, according to their karmic conditions. Some parents are reborn in the Human Realm, the Animal Realm or the Hell Realm, while the baby spirits have no one to help them ascend spiritually to a better realm. Therefore, they are transferred to the Hell of Iron Mountains, where they are left to roam and cry until the courts of the Underworld have finally arranged their rebirth. That's why the punishment for those who commit sexual misconduct and abortions is so severe.

If these offenders recited the Buddha's holy name and sincerely repented while they were still alive, even though the negative karma that had been created cannot be completely eliminated, they would still be reborn as humans after serving their time in Hell.

The majority of the offenders here, however, will be reborn in the Animal Realm after serving their time.

Master: They are all real (subsequent content omitted).

This section outlines the serious spiritual and karmic repercussions of abortion, as explained through Master Lu's teachings. Aborted and miscarried children do not disappear. They become lingering spirits attached to the mother or family members, often causing physical illnesses, emotional instability, infertility, and misfortunes such as financial decline or family conflict. These spirits, having been denied their rightful birth, carry resentment and become karmic debt collectors, manifesting in various forms of suffering. In severe cases, they can even possess living children or contribute to developmental disorders. This section emphasizes that these consequences cannot be resolved through ordinary means; only by sincerely repenting and reciting Little Houses and Buddhist scriptures can one help these spirits ascend and gradually restore peace, health, and harmony in one's life.

From Died Fertilized Egg to an Aborted Fetus, All Require Spirit Ascension

Q&A 14. Embryo Formation Without Birth Is Still Considered Miscarriage [37]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Dec. 9, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! A fellow Buddhist practitioner had a dream where many pregnant women came to her house for a meal. She is currently reciting Buddhist scriptures to help her miscarried children ascend. Does this dream mean there are many children who need ascending?

Master: If she is in the process of helping her own aborted or miscarried children ascend, and many pregnant women appear in her dream, it means that each pregnant woman represents a child. I have talked about this before: for ordinary people who are not knowledgeable in medicine, whenever a couple engages in intercourse and an embryo is unintentionally formed, even if the pregnancy does not come to term, it still counts as a miscarriage.

In her case, she may have had many such incidents unknowingly, resulting in many spiritual children. This is spiritually equivalent to abortion in terms of the need for scripture recitation.

Caller: Then, how many Little Houses does she need to recite?

Master: How many pregnant women did she see?

Caller: She did not say, just that there were many.

Master: Many... It probably was not 100, right? Maybe around 50? Then go with $5 \times 7 = 35$... about 350 Little Houses.

Q&A 15. Taking Birth Control Pills May Result in Killing Life [38]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on August 16, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! I had a dream where someone was reading my totem, and then they said to me, "You have more than 20 children." I suddenly felt terrified and creeped out. My husband was also there and said, "Yes, you do have more than 20 children."

Master: Oh no! That means you must have taken some kind of birth control pills in the past!

Caller: In real life, I have only given birth to one daughter. She was my first. As for medications, I have taken birth control pills twice.

Master: That's the problem! Those two times definitely count, 100% certain! Taking those pills causes this. Once an embryo begins to form, those pills immediately kill it. So, taking such medication is quite serious. It would have been better to prevent fertilization in the first place, which would not constitute killing.

Using medication can result in the loss of life. Any sexual activity followed by the use of such pills has this potential consequence. Even relying on the so-called "safe period" might result in flushing away a formed embryo.

Q&A 16. Miscarried Child of Mother Attached to the Son-Little House Should Be Addressed to His Own Karmic Creditor [39]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 25, 2016)

Caller: Hello, Master Lu! I would like to ask: if my mother's miscarried child is now attached to me, how should I address the Little House?

Master: If your mother's miscarried child is now attached to you and has nothing to do with her anymore, then the Little House should be addressed to "your name's karmic creditor." Because the child is now on you, not your mother, the karmic burden has transferred to you. That means you are now responsible for it (Rest of conversation omitted).

Q&A 17. IVF Also Counts as Miscarriage [40]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 2, 2012)

Caller: I have recited over 80 Little Houses for my miscarried child. In the past, I underwent IVF, but I do not know how many embryos were involved...

Master: Do you still dream of children nowadays?

Caller: After reciting those Little Houses, I still occasionally dream of them.

Master: In your dreams, do the children appear happy when they leave, or are they unhappy?

Caller: Some seem happy, but others do not.

Master: Those who appear unhappy have not left yet. With IVF, many of the embryos are actually alive but do not survive, so they all count...

Q&A 18. Miscarriage and Abortion Can Lead to Infertility [41]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on May 17, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! How many Little Houses do I need to recite in order to become pregnant?

Master: In general, difficulty conceiving is related to past abortions or miscarriages.

Caller: I have never had an abortion.

Master: Generally speaking, that is what it refers to. But just because you personally have not had an abortion does not mean that you and your current husband have not lost a child together. Sometimes, once an embryo is formed, a spirit enters it. Also, many people use methods after marriage that kill the child, especially taking medication, which causes the death of the child. These all count as deceased children. If you do not help them ascend, it is very difficult to conceive.

Caller: How many Little Houses should I recite?

Master: You must continuously make great vows. For example, tell Guan Yin Bodhisattva, "I sincerely wish to have a child. When the child grows up, I will let him promote Buddhism. I will guide others and spread the Dharma..." You need to say such things. Vague or meaningless words will not help. Recite the Little Houses diligently. For your daily practice, recite 21 times the *Great Compassion Mantra*, 21 times the *Heart Sutra* as the foundation. Recite *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* times and also recite more *Ru Yi Bao Lun Wang Tuo Luo Ni* (如意宝轮王陀罗尼).

Caller: Should the Little Houses be addressed to "my name's child" or "my name's karmic creditor"?

Master: Either one is fine. Do not be anxious. This sort of matter depends on karmic affinity. For you, the best time is from April to August. I am not doing totem readings today, but this message just came through, so I am telling you: April to August gives you the highest chance of conception. You must also perform life liberation. Have you done any?

Caller: Yes, today I released one kilogram of fish roe. How much more fish should I release?

Master: Release as much as you can. The more you release, the more effective it will be. The more you recite scriptures, the more effective it is. (Next caller joins) (The caller requests a blessing for her gynecological discomfort.)

That is caused by karmic debts and interfering spirits. With spirits causing trouble, how can you conceive? You must recite until you feel very well: Happy and peaceful. When your energy and mood improve significantly, it becomes much easier to conceive.

Q&A 19. How to Judge If an Aborted Child Has Been Successfully Ascended [42]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 25, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! My mother wants to know if the spirit of the aborted child has been ascended, but she has not had any relevant dreams. How can she tell?

Master: It is very simple. If she has not had any dreams, but she feels at ease and no longer senses the child's presence, then it is likely the child has been ascended. If she still feels guilty, uneasy, or uncertain, and is still seeking confirmation, then the spirit has not left. It is that simple.

For example, someone recites 20 Little Houses but keeps worrying that the spirit has not ascended. In that case, it most likely has not. But if someone recites 50 Little Houses, then it is almost certain the spirit has ascended. It would be hard for it not to with that amount.

Caller: Oh, I have not had any dreams. Last time I called the totem hotline, you said the spirit was still present, so I kept reciting, but I am not sure when to stop.

Master: Keep reciting. In many cases, if no dreams occur, the spirit may have already left.

Q&A 20. Dreams Indicating Whether a Child Has Been Ascended [43]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 15, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! If I dream of the child I am trying to help ascend, does it mean the child has not been ascended yet?

Master: It depends on the context of the dream. If you dream that the child you are reciting for is happily leaving, such as taking a train or plane, then the spirit has been ascended. If the child belongs to you and someone else takes them away, that also means the spirit has been successfully ascended.

Caller: I have not had an abortion or miscarriage, but I dreamed of a child. A fellow practitioner told me to recite 7 Little Houses. After I finished, I dreamed of being pregnant again, as if I were about to give birth.

Master: Dreaming of pregnancy usually means the spirit is about to be ascended. If you dream that the child belongs to someone else and not to you anymore, then the spirit has already ascended.

Q&A 21. It Is Best to Address Little Houses to “So-and-So’s Child” When Ascending a Miscarried Baby [44]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 27, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! For spirits on me, karmic creditors in dreams, aborted children, and the deceased, can I address all the Little Houses simply as “my name’s karmic creditor”? Because I am not sure how many each one needs.

Master: That is acceptable, no problem. However, if the spirit is a child, it is best to write “So-and-so’s child” because some child spirits may not receive them otherwise. Other karmic creditors might claim them first, as these little spirits are weak and have no power. They may end up causing trouble for you.

Caller: I have had four abortions. How many Little Houses should I recite for them?

Master: At least 49.

Caller: For each child?

Master: No, 49 in total.

Q&A 22. If an Aborted Child Reincarnates as an Animal, Further Ascending Is Still Required [45]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on May 19, 2013)

Caller: A listener helped a miscarried child ascend, but the child reincarnated as a monkey. You told them they still needed to continue the ascending, or else they would suffer a serious illness in old age. Is it because monkeys have short lifespans and, after dying, may come back to seek revenge?

Master: That is entirely possible. One possibility is that the spirit comes back after the monkey dies. Another is that it starts troubling the person even before the monkey dies.

Q&A 23. What Kind of Karmic Relationship Remains Between a mother and Her Aborted Child After the Child Is Ascended and Reborn [46]?

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 27, 2011)

Caller: Hello, Master! Generally, if an aborted child is sufficiently ascended, they can be reborn. After rebirth, will they still have any karmic ties with the mother or the family?

Master: Yes, that is a very good question. Absolutely, they will. If they are reborn, they will definitely be reborn near their mother’s relatives. The mother will feel particularly fond of that baby because she owes them and keeps giving them money. Sometimes it even results in a May-December romance. Why do some women become extremely attached to a certain man? In fact, it is because that man is her aborted child, and she owes him. In the end, he abandons her, and she becomes so heartbroken that she wants to die for him. That is karmic repayment.

Caller: I see. So, there is a relationship of debt repayment involved.

Master: Exactly the same.

Q&A 24. Why an Aborted Child’s Spirit Remains Even After Years of Recitation [47]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Oct. 25, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! I feel like the spirit of the aborted child has not left. I have been doing recitation for years, and it still seems like he is around. Lately, I even feel like he has returned. I plan to recite 49 Little Houses for him. Do I need to make a vow or pray to the Bodhisattva, or do anything else?

Master: Yes, you do. If the aborted child has not left, there are two possible reasons. One: The karmic entanglement between you and him is too deep, and he refuses to leave because he wants revenge. Two: The number of Little Houses is insufficient. Those are the two reasons.

Caller: Would 49 Little Houses be enough?

Master: Not enough. If he has not left, and you only give 49? You need to offer him 108 sheets!

Q&A 25. Aborted Children Become Homeless Spirits and Fall into Tragic Realms [48]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on April 12, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! If a soul came to be born but the mother aborted it, then the child ends up reborn into the Beast Realm. The child never even lived or committed any actions. How can that happen?

Master: If the family rejects the child, isn't that child essentially an orphan? Let me give a simple analogy: If you want to return home but your family does not accept you, you would be sent to a shelter, randomly assigned somewhere. You have already been downgraded. A child who should have been born gets aborted and killed. That is karmic retribution. Since he was killed, isn't it natural that he would fall into the Beast Realm? He is no longer considered human. That is why abortion is such a serious sin. It is very pitiful!

Q&A 26. Aborted Fetuses Become Wandering Spirits and Cannot Reincarnate [49]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Dec. 30, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! You said that aborted children do not have a "license" in the underworld, so they cannot be judged. Usually, only through ascension can they be released; otherwise, they remain wandering spirits. If an aborted child's spirit is released from the mother's body through ascension, are they still wandering spirits? Even after being ascended, the underworld still cannot judge them?

Master: That child will not remain a wandering spirit forever. For example, that child originally came to the human world to be born, and they had a destined lifespan. When that lifespan ends, they will reincarnate. So, it is not that they will be a wandering spirit forever. However, during the wandering period, if you recite Buddhist scriptures and ascend them in advance, they can be allocated a spot to reincarnate. Because of their merits and virtues, they can reincarnate earlier.

Caller: So, if they have enough energy, they may reincarnate early. Otherwise, if their destined life is decades long, they have to wait that long?

Master: Exactly.

Q&A 27. One Must Repent Sincerely When Helping Miscarried or Aborted Children to Ascend [50]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Dec. 15, 2017)

Caller: Hello, Master! During the Auckland Dharma Conference, you read the totem for a Buddhist friend and enlightened her that she had aborted five children. After reciting around 500 Little Houses, there were still two children who had not ascended. May I ask why it took more than 400 Little Houses to help only three of them ascend?

Master: First, rule out the quality of the Little Houses. If the quality is good, then it is likely that the abortion itself was extremely cruel. The doctor may have crushed the baby's bones during the procedure.

Caller: Yes, that is correct.

Master: In that case, it is equivalent to having the child utterly torn apart. That is the first reason. The second is that after the child died, he never received any Little Houses or karmic repayment. He lingered with her all along. If a large karmic debt remains unpaid for a long time, won't there be interest?

Caller: Yes, there will be.

Master: The interest keeps accumulating, compounding. So, tell me, would 21 Little Houses be enough in the end?

Caller: Definitely not.

Master: The spirit holds deep resentment. He came to be reborn, yet was killed. With nowhere to go, he became a lonely wandering ghost. So, he keeps haunting her!

Caller: I understand. Master, is it also because the mother did not sincerely recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*?

Master: That is right. Without sincere repentance, just reciting the Little Houses will not work. I gave an example before: if you ran over someone's child and then say, "I will just pay you money," the parent might say, "No! I want you to be in jail. You won't even admit you were wrong? I do not want your filthy money. I want my child's life! If you do not admit fault, I want you punished!" Jail time is not the same as money. Reciting Little Houses is like paying compensation, but if you do not recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, you are not admitting guilt. You have to say sincerely, "I am sorry! I truly repent! I was wrong to do this. I sincerely apologize to you." Then, combined with compensation, the matter can be resolved.

Caller: Oh, I understand. When burning Little Houses for the aborted child, how many times should we recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*?

Master: It depends. Everyone should recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*. Before reciting, you must say aloud: "I am reciting this for the child I aborted. Today, I sincerely repent through the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*. I acknowledge the wrong I committed in having an abortion." Many people are not sincere, which is why the spirit does not leave. Some won't even say the word "abortion." They just say things like "I had a miscarriage," "I do not know what happened," or even deny it. This infuriates the spirit. It is like killing someone and then lying in court. The spirit becomes even more enraged and demands harsher punishment.

Caller: I understand. If someone has aborted or unintentionally miscarried a child but has not received a totem reading from the Master, how can they determine how many Little Houses to offer?

Master: Sincere repentance. The spirits are always nearby, watching how sincere you are. Offer more, say, 49 Little Houses. Say, "Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I am sorry. I am truly sorry for aborting my child. I feel deep remorse." One woman had two abortions. Later, she said she felt terribly guilty. Every time she recited the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, she cried and sincerely thought of her child, feeling sorry. Not long after, she dreamed that a small child was carried away by someone. The child even waved goodbye

to her. In the dream, she knew she was the mother, although she did not recognize the child. You must be sincere. Sincere moves Heaven and Earth.

Caller: I understand. Without a totem reading from the Master, how should we pray to Bodhisattvas in hopes of receiving a dream from the Bodhisattva or the Master, indicating the number of Little Houses, or even seeing them mediate the case?

Master: Recite sincerely and wholeheartedly. Rely on your accumulated merits and virtues. A person who consistently does good will find blessings in adversity and turn misfortune into fortune. If you do not cultivate regularly and just cling to the Buddha's feet in moments of crisis, what is the use?

Caller: I understand now. Thank you, Master, for your compassionate teachings.

This section further highlights the profound karmic consequences of abortion and miscarriage, emphasizing that even unrecognized embryo formation can result in the presence of spiritual beings requiring ascension. Master Lu teaches that taking birth control pills or undergoing IVF may unknowingly lead to the creation and destruction of numerous lives, each being possessed by a soul. These spirits may attach to the mother, her children or her relatives, causing health issues, emotional disturbances, or infertility. Spiritual ascension through the recitation of Little Houses and sincere repentance using the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* is essential. Without heartfelt apology and acknowledgment of the wrongdoing, these spirits often refuse to leave. The section warns that karmic entanglements persist even after rebirth and stresses the importance of vigilant Dharma practice to resolve these hidden causes of suffering.

Result

Case 1. My miscarried child came in my dreams asking for little houses

I encountered the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in July 2012. Before that, I had no religious beliefs and rarely visited temples.

One day in March or April 2012, I suddenly dreamed of Guan Yin Bodhisattva dressed in white, descending from the sky on auspicious clouds. She walked up to me and asked, "Are you doing well?" I replied, "Pretty well." She said a few more things, but sadly, I forgot them after waking. About ten days later, I dreamed of the Maitreya Buddha. He told me, "You must smile"-as if to say, no matter what you face, keep smiling. Then He gave me a big, joyful smile, and I smiled with Him until I woke up. In those days, I was very happy, wondering why I had suddenly dreamed of two Buddhas. A little over two months later, a colleague introduced me to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

When I learned that this Dharma Door was created by Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I suddenly realized that She had appeared in my dreams to enlighten me. A few months later, a major upheaval hit my family. My father fell ill, and many other troubles followed. During that exhausting and painful time, I finally understood why

the Maitreya Buddha told me to smile. He knew what I was about to face and was encouraging me. My gratitude is beyond words.

Since I officially began reciting Buddhist scriptures in August 2012, I have had many spiritual responses and wonderful, auspicious dreams. These experiences are familiar to many fellow Buddhist practitioners, so I will not go into detail. But over the past week, I had two very miraculous dreams that I feel compelled to share, to help fellow practitioners and anyone who still doubts the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door believe in its incredible power and efficacy. This Dharma Door is truly worth following and protecting for life.

The first dream: A week ago, I dreamed that I was with a few friends in a serene place of green mountains and clear water, having tea and chatting in a small pavilion atop a hill. It was drizzling lightly, and when the rain stopped, a stunning rainbow appeared in the sky, which was much more vivid than any rainbow I had ever seen. Everyone rushed to the railing to admire it.

Suddenly, a cloud-like white mass drifted down from the rainbow. Everyone excitedly called out, "Come here, float over to me!" I was also included. To my surprise, it floated right into my arms. Then, from within, a baby's head, around 8 or 9 months old, emerged. The child was incredibly adorable and smiled at me lovingly. I instantly knew: This was the child I had miscarried.

I said, "Would you like to come back to be my baby? Mommy loves you."

She replied, "It is not the time yet. It might explode."

Then she asked, "Mommy, can you help me ascend?"

I was stunned. She continued, "That means reciting Little Houses."

I quickly answered, "Yes, I can! I will definitely recite them for you. Mommy really, really loves you."

She beamed with joy and, blushing shyly, said, "100 Little Houses would be a lot." Then she turned her head away, too bashful to look at me.

I replied, "Mommy will definitely recite them for you."

After that, she disappeared.

A friend beside me asked, "What were you talking about? We could not understand your language."

The next morning, I stood before the Buddhist altar and made a vow to Guan Yin Bodhisattva that I would recite 100 Little Houses for my miscarried child and prayed Her to protect the child.

This year is my zodiac year. I am 36. I had previously vowed to recite 36 Little Houses by June to help resolve my zodiac-year karmic obstacle. I planned to alternate weekly: One week for karmic creditors, one week for my miscarried child. Once the 36 sheets were completed, I would focus entirely on the child's ascending.

This week happened to be for reciting Little Houses for karmic creditors. But this morning, I had another remarkable dream.

The second dream: I was walking through a plaza, and the sky was full of auspicious signs: Auspicious beasts and small animals. Suddenly, something shot down from the sky and landed in my arms. It transformed into my miscarried child. This time, she appears slightly older, around one year old. I held her in my arms with great love.

She said, "Thank you, Mommy, for reciting Buddhist scriptures to help me ascend." I was confused. "I have not gotten to it yet," I thought.

Really, she pouted and grumbled, "It was only 20 minutes!"

I quickly explained, "Mommy made a vow to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to recite 36 Little Houses to overcome this zodiac-year karmic obstacle. Until I finish them, I will alternate and recite some for you. Once those 36 are done, I will focus entirely on you. Is that okay?"

She nodded and said, "Okay then." And with that, she vanished.

Upon waking up this morning, I knew I had to share these two dreams. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and Little Houses are truly miraculous. To have encountered this Dharma Door in this life is the greatest blessing. We must cherish it and use this precious time to recite Little Houses and help our miscarried children.

In the past, we were ignorant and harmed them. Now that we know about Little Houses, we can, with Guan Yin Bodhisattva's compassion and our own efforts, help these pitiful spirits ascend. Letting them reincarnate into better realms is our responsibility and obligation.

With deepest respect,

Buddhist practitioner: Y132

Comments: This case offers direct, firsthand evidence that the spirit of an aborted baby requires Little Houses to ascend.

Spirits or Heavenly beings who come to be reborn into a family do so either as a result of positive karmic affinity (善缘) or negative karmic affinity (恶缘). The former repays kindness; the latter collects karmic debts.

Case 2. Ascending aborted baby has benefited me and my family

I first came into contact with the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door through a good friend's recommendation in February 2023. Both my husband and I began our journey with this Dharma Door at the same time. Initially, after hearing about my friend's personal experience with practicing Buddhism, I became interested in the Dharma and found it quite fascinating. Subsequently, I officially started my practice of learning Buddhism and reciting Buddhist scriptures.

Before contacting Buddhism, my relationship with my husband was not harmonious. We often argue over trivial matters in our daily lives. Our son was disobedient, frequently opposing me. His concentration in studies was lacking; he wrote slowly, and he did not heed advice. To ensure that he could complete his homework

on time, I resigned from my job to stay at home full-time, but the household still remained chaotic.

Even though he had just entered the first grade, sometimes homework extended past 9p.m. His excessive energy often led to him being active until very late, causing complaints from neighbours.

In summary, I felt that I was failing in both marriage and parenting. This brought me distress and confusion, and I could not comprehend it. I felt that my life was a failure.

In the past, due to a lack of understanding of karma, I had a miscarriage. After I started practicing Buddhism, a Buddhist friend told me that conflicts between spouses and disturbances from my son were closely related to the abortion I had. They suggested that I should recite Buddhist scriptures to ascend the child who was miscarried.

I believe in the Buddhist teachings and am willing to practice Buddhism and recite scriptures. Later, I made a vow to adopt a vegetarian diet. My husband has had a deep affinity with Buddhism since childhood. Eventually, he also made a vow to follow a vegetarian lifestyle. Grateful for the compassionate blessings of the Bodhisattva, allowing us to practice Buddhism together as a couple. Friends say that both of us had spiritual cultivation from past lives, and this is a rare Buddhist affinity that we should cherish deeply!

In August, we set up a Buddhist altar at home, and we are deeply grateful to the kind-hearted Buddhist friends who freely provided us with the Buddhist altar, statues, and other articles for worship. The Buddhist altar in our home is very dignified, and now I offer incense to the Bodhisattvas every day, bringing a true sense of Dharma joy and fulfilment through the practice of the Dharma!

Actually, I have had health issues since childhood, and giving birth felt like I lost half of my life. I also had gynecological problems. After practicing Buddhism and reciting Buddhist scriptures, my health has improved. For example, I have recovered from allergic rhinitis that troubled me for over 20 years. My digestive system has improved, and the mysterious abdominal bloating I had for 2 years has miraculously disappeared. I no longer suffer from constipation, and my lower back pain and stiffness have eased. The pain in my left leg and knee has also improved. Overall, I feel more energetic than before. Not only that, but our marital relationship has also improved. Since practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures, we hardly ever argue. All of this is attributed to the teachings of Buddhism. The benefits of Buddhism are truly profound and genuine!

The changes in my child are truly miraculous. Previously, he would playfully use his head to bump into my stomach, causing me distress and tears. When I tried to discipline him, he would talk back and confront me defiantly. Despite trying various methods, I could not address the root of the issue. After practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures, repaying Little Houses for the miscarried child and the karmic creditors of my son, there has been a gradual transformation in him. He no longer bumps his head into my stomach, completes his homework more quickly, and, most notably, his concentration has improved. Previously, he used to

come home from school and immediately start playing, but now he comes home and focuses on studying. I can hardly believe how quickly he has changed! He is more obedient, sleeps earlier than before, and sometimes even recites Buddhist scriptures and reads Buddhist teachings like *Words of Wisdom*, offering incense to the Bodhisattvas. I am truly grateful for the teachings of Buddhism! I understand that all these positive changes are the compassionate blessings and empowerment of Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

Grateful for the compassionate blessings of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, grateful to Master Lu for bringing such profound Buddhist teachings to the world, saving us, the suffering beings! Without encountering Buddhism, perhaps I would still be living a chaotic life! The days without Buddhism are ones I hesitate to even think about... Besides gratitude, there is only more gratitude!

After gaining a clear understanding through Buddhist teachings, I learned that killing leads to a shortened lifespan and various illnesses. Therefore, I strive to abstain from killing and engage in life liberation. Adopting a vegetarian diet is not only beneficial for our physical well-being but also reflects compassion, contributing to our overall health, both physically and mentally. Consequently, I choose to follow a vegetarian lifestyle. Additionally, reciting Buddhist scriptures can help alleviate karmic debts. Recognizing that obstacles in our lives may stem from karmic hindrances, I am committed to reciting the Little House for my karmic creditors. Through studying *Buddhism in plain Terms* and the enlightenment of Master Lu, I have acquired valuable Dharma knowledge. I deeply appreciate Master Lu's insightful teachings, which have brought significant benefits to my life.

It is truly a great fortune across multiple lifetimes for me to encounter Buddhism and come across such an auspicious and efficacious Dharma Door. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door does not charge a single cent; it allows us to address life's challenges through reciting Buddhist scriptures, making vows, and performing life liberation. I have genuinely benefited a lot from it!

Buddhism is truly miraculous! I remember the night I made a vow to adopt a vegetarian diet; that very night, Bodhisattva conveyed a dream to me, revealing the situation of an elder family member. Shortly after, the events in the dream manifested in reality. Since practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures, the Bodhisattva sometimes gives us prophetic dreams, allowing us to recite Buddhist scriptures in advance to resolve potential calamities. When I was ascending my miscarried child, I had several dreams. In one of them, it seemed like the child was about to depart. I thought perhaps it was through such experiences that my son underwent positive changes.

Guan Yin Bodhisattva is truly compassionate. When I had been practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures for 4 months, the Bodhisattva conveyed a dream to me, indicating that my son had an age 369 predestined calamity. Upon waking, I cried deeply and immediately sought Guan Yin Bodhisattva's help. Through the Four Golden Buddhist Practices of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door: Reciting Buddhist scriptures, making vows, performing life

liberation, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, the Bodhisattva blessed my child to overcome this calamity. I am profoundly grateful for the compassionate salvation of Guan Yin Bodhisattva from the depths of my heart!

I genuinely feel that the teachings of Buddhism are boundless, and the presence of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas is genuine and not illusory. The more one practices, the more one benefits, and the sooner one begins this journey, the earlier the benefits are realized!

Lastly, I want to mention a good friend. In fact, we have not seen each other for 6 or 7 years. We were close friends and best friends since high school. After that, we both stayed in our hometown, lost contact, and had no news of each other. Over these years, we both secretly thought about each other. However, without contact information or knowing each other's addresses, it seemed impossible to reconnect. At the end of 2022, one day while shopping at the supermarket, I unexpectedly ran into her. At first, I hesitated to recognize her, afraid of making a mistake... Later, she told me that our meeting was thanks to her prayers to the Bodhisattva. She had said to the Bodhisattva, "I want to meet my friend. If we meet, I will transform her into practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures."

Fate is truly miraculous, with mysterious arrangements beyond our control! Moreover, my husband later revealed that he had been considering practicing Buddhism and reciting scriptures before the new year, but he could not find a suitable Dharma Door. Suddenly, at this moment, my good friend appeared. All these coincidences are the compassionate arrangements of the Bodhisattva! I am truly grateful for this extraordinary connection!

In the future, I will undoubtedly persevere in my studies and practice, respecting my Master and upholding the Dharma. I will diligently progress on this path, never turning back. I hope my sharing can transform more sentient beings having affinity with Buddha to enter the Buddhist path, have faith in Buddhism, recite Buddhist scriptures, deeply believe in karma, benefit from recitation, change their destiny, and find happiness beyond suffering.

I, not my fellow Buddhist practitioners, will be responsible for my own karma!

Buddhist practitioner Z133, Gratitude and Namaste!

Comments: A miscarried or aborted child can lead to family discord and disobedient behaviour in children [16]. This case provides new supporting evidence for our earlier argument. The child banging his head against his mother's abdomen was driven by the influence of the aborted baby's spirit. Similarly, his other abnormal behaviours were also caused by the aborted baby's spirit. After the spirit was ascended through Dharma practice, family harmony was restored, the child became obedient, and her many physical ailments also improved.

Case 3. Repenting for abortions improved my health and family harmony

Before I started practicing Buddhism, I had never been to a temple or participated in any Buddhist activities. It was in April

or May of 2019 when I began practicing Buddhism and chanting Buddhist scriptures. Before that, I had never imagined that I would one day learn Buddhism and chant scriptures...

For decades, those who knew me knew that I enjoyed all kinds of meat dishes and did not like eating vegetarian food at all. Interestingly, just after practicing Buddhism and chanting scriptures for 4-5 months, I found myself unable to eat meat anymore. Whenever I ate meat, I would vomit, sometimes accompanied by stomach pain. At first, I thought it was due to my stomach problems. However, as it happened more frequently, I realized that it was due to the compassionate blessings of Bodhisattvas; the karmic conditions for me to adopt a fully vegetarian diet had ripened!

On the first day of April in the lunar calendar year 2020, I formally made a lifelong vow to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to adhere to a fully vegetarian diet. I am grateful for the Bodhisattva's compassion, which has enabled me to cherish and respect all sentient beings from then on, and to no longer harbor any resentment towards animals!

Before I embraced Buddhism, I was ignorant of the law of cause and effect. I did not take abortion seriously at all and could not even remember how many children I had aborted. It was the Bodhisattva who enlightened me through a dream: I saw 6-7 poor, ragged children in the dark, both boys and girls. Upon awakening, I remembered the scene from the dream, and tears welled up uncontrollably. Every time I recalled the scene from the dream, my heart ached terribly, often leading to tears. I am grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for compassionately guiding me to see them and enabling me to sincerely repent my past misdeeds.

I earnestly advise everyone against abortion. The souls of aborted fetuses have nowhere to go, and their situation is extremely tragic. Often, these spirits will attach themselves to the bodies of the mothers who aborted them. Over time, this attachment can lead to health issues in the mother, especially in the waist, back, shoulders, and gynecological areas, and it may even affect any subsequent children! The law of cause and effect is real, not imaginary!

During the Qingming Festival in 2020, I experienced severe abdominal pain. I prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to bless me and relieve my pain. I hoped Guan Yin Bodhisattva would assist me in swiftly ascending these unfortunate children to a better place! After making my vow, the pain in my stomach disappeared! It was truly miraculous; Guan Yin Bodhisattva always responds to prayers!

Later, I made a vow to recite the Little House for them, either 7 or 21 sheets, to ascend them. However, there were interruptions during the recitations: when I was free, I recited more, and when I was busy, I recited less.

Later, around June or July 2020, I vowed to release 1,000 fish under slaughter for the aborted children, and I gradually fulfilled this vow. At that time, I did not know that unless prompted by dreams or if the deceased were within the first 49 days after passing, fish releases are not the usual means of ascension; typically, Little House is used for ascending.

During this time, I dreamt of 5 children being ascended: One boy was escorted away by a woman, one girl departed on her own, two girls were pushed away by a woman in a car, and another woman gave birth to a boy.

At the end of 2020, I dreamt of two more children, and I vowed to recite 2x49 Little Houses to ascend them. After completing this, I continued by vowing to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to recite 108 Little Houses to ascend them. Afterwards, I rarely dreamt of children again...

At the end of 2022, I allocated 0.5% of the merits and virtues gained from being vegetarian for over two years to ascend the spirits of aborted fetuses.

Around the Qingming Festival in 2023, I dreamt of a child. Upon awakening, I vowed to recite a set of 21 Little Houses to ascend the spirit of the aborted fetus. Later, unsure if the ascension had been completed, I made another vow to recite another batch of 21 Little Houses.

In mid-July, I dreamt of three children bathing by the riverbank. Once again, I vowed to recite a batch of 49 Little Houses combined with 108 recitations of the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* to ascend them. During this period, I dreamt of one child among a crowd, and a woman came to take the child away. The child happily followed her. Since then, I have not dreamt of children anymore...

I made a vow to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, sincerely repenting for the negative karma I had accumulated. I am deeply sorry for what I have done to these children! I vowed to recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 49 times for the first set, 49 times for the second set, and 108 times for the third set, and eventually completed all the vows.

Through sincere repentance and reciting scriptures to ascend the aborted children, my physical condition has improved, and my family has become more harmonious. Previously, I was in constant pain and suffering. After embracing Buddhism, my health improved, and I became more cheerful.

I helped my husband recite Little Houses for his karmic creditors, and his health also improved. Before, my husband would completely change after drinking, and he would even hit me. Now, even if he drinks, he no longer hits me and takes care of the family. Previously, my husband's attitude was "when one person eats, the whole family is not hungry." He only cared about spending money on himself and did not care about me and our son. Now, he has undergone significant changes and is reluctant to spend money outside. Our relationship has also become increasingly harmonious. All gratitude to the tangible transformation brought about by my Buddhist practice and recitation of scriptures!

I hope those who have yet to embrace Buddhism and recite scriptures will quickly pick up the Buddhist scriptures. I have not come across any other Dharma Doors, but in my heart, Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is the most efficacious and supreme! I am fortunate to have encountered the teachings of Buddhism, and I am

grateful for the compassionate salvation of Guan Yin Bodhisattva and my Master. I vow to follow Guan Yin Bodhisattva and my Master in practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, never to regress!

I, not my fellow Buddhist practitioners, will be responsible for my own karma!

Buddhist practitioner: W134, Gratitude and Namaste!

Comments: When the spirit of an aborted baby is successfully ascended, there is often a noticeable sense of relief or confirmation. Dreams frequently serve as an indication of this success.

Once again, the spirit of an aborted baby can cause family discord and health problems. After the spirit is properly ascended, family harmony is restored, and health conditions improve.

Case 4. Ascending my 6 aborted and miscarried children by 1188 little houses

Before I encountered the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my son would frequently have fevers, sometimes even requiring hospitalization, averaging once every three months. Besides feeling heartbroken, what more could I do for him? Watching the nurse instruct me to hold his legs as she prepared to insert the needle, he cried and looked at me, seeking rescue. Oh, my child... My heart ached as if struck by a hammer, wishing I could take the needle on his behalf. Hearing him call out for his mother, tears streamed down my face. Sleepless all night, I waited for my mother to arrive to take care of him. Exhausted and unable to let go, I headed to work, truly feeling the pain, a heart-wrenching pain.

This was not even the worst part. When my son was three, he had a febrile seizure in the middle of the night, his whole body shaking and eyes rolling back. I was terrified... Though usually strong, I rushed to my mother with him in my arms. My mother jumped out of bed, and my grandmother kept calling his name. I went to the room to grab the documents, preparing to take him to the emergency room. My mind went blank, unsure of what to take. My mother yelled, "Hurry up!" I snapped back to reality and rushed him to the emergency room. Still in my pajamas, helmet on, I ran to the nurse, saying, "Please save my child! Save my child!" The nurse checked his eyes and felt him, saying, "Mom, your child is okay, just passed out." My mother arrived shortly after. Remembering the seizure, it felt like the end of the world.

Not to mention his performance in class, he could not concentrate, and his grades were poor. Whether he was playing outside or at home, he was constantly moving around. Before I started practicing Buddhism, I did not understand anything. My son was affected by the spirits of aborted children, and despite spending a lot of money on ritual ceremonies to help them ascend, it was ineffective...

After encountering the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I began reciting Buddhist scriptures and dreamt of the aborted children in a dark and cold place, asking me what I was chanting. I told them it was Guan Yin Bodhisattva's scriptures, which are very good and can eliminate karmic obstacles and ascend the deceased. They were

eager to be ascended, and the karmic creditors were in a hurry. I could only recite Little Houses after work because I had just started learning, and I needed to read the scripture books to avoid making mistakes with the *Great Compassion Mantra*. Because they were anxious, my head hurt.

Once, I dreamt of being strangled and unable to breathe. In the dream, I chanted "Guan Yin Bodhisattva." Guan Yin Bodhisattva let me hear the voices of the aborted children crying for help, like a tornado, very dark, pulling them into a bottomless pit. They grabbed my throat, their feet hanging in the air, crying, "Mom, save me." It was the aborted children being sucked down. Suddenly, my right hand became powerful and large, grabbing the child's chest, pulling him up, and gently placing him beside me. I found it was my real-life child I had grabbed up, and I gently put him next to me.

One time, I woke up in the middle of the night. The aborted children would not let me sleep and kept bothering me. When I opened my eyes, they jumped under the table to hide. Awake, I heard the table shaking, knowing it was the aborted children hiding.

In another dream, one of the aborted children had a lot of resentment. In the dream, my real son was walking around, talking to himself. I could not understand his language, so I recorded it, calling him continuously. He could not hear me, his eyes vacant, walking back and forth. I took him to see a fellow practitioner. Suddenly, the scene shifted, and 3 male Buddhist practitioners appeared, using a large LCD TV and professional equipment to play back the incomprehensible language. The practitioner told me that Master Lu had these devices. When the LCD TV was playing, a small boy in thin, old clothes appeared on the screen, kneeling and crying miserably. He was missing a piece of flesh from his thigh, crying that he had waited 1,000 years for a chance to be born, and I aborted him. 1,000 years ago, his mother also aborted him, and he had been waiting a long time, a millennium. He was very resentful and cried sadly. I held him, heartbroken.

I kept saying how terrible and cruel I was to have killed my own child. How could I be so cruel... I was in a daze at work, mentally exhausted. I kept blaming myself, thinking I was not human for doing such a thing. The aborted children were in so much pain; I was not human... I was in a daze all day, unable to focus on work, constantly blaming myself. I was so sad, unable to pull myself together.

I recited 21 Little Houses for the first aborted child. My mother dreamt of a very wealthy and famous actress holding a baby boy, smiling happily, telling my mother that this was her child. My mother said, "Didn't you have a daughter?" In reality, this actress had a daughter. The actress happily said it was her child. My mother joyfully congratulated her.

I recited 49 Little Houses for the second aborted child. Again, my mother dreamt of the same actress holding a baby boy, happily telling my mother this was her child. My mother responded again, "Didn't you have a daughter?" The actress happily said it was her child. My mother joyfully said, "Congratulations!"

The third child required 400 Little Houses, the fourth needed 600, and I vowed to recite 1,000. During the repayment process, I dreamt of a fifth boy crying in the bathroom. This was just before the New Year, and my son and I both dreamt of family members eliminating karma by washing clothes, cleaning toilets, brushing teeth, and washing the sink, eating glutinous rice balls and noodles. The house was beautifully decorated. Suddenly, a small boy was crying sadly, looking at me. I vowed to recite 49 Little Houses for him.

Later, I dreamt of a sixth girl whom I aborted. She was crying on our house's balcony on the washing machine. She was in great pain, and my mother cried, feeling sorry for her aborted granddaughter. My mother blamed herself, crying and telling me, "The aborted child is so pitiful and is also crying." She felt she had failed to teach me well. The girl required 69 Little Houses. I made a vow to recite 69 Little Houses for her.

In reality, I had four abortions, but I also took birth control pills, which resulted in two more appearing in my dreams. Taking birth control pills incurs the karma of killing. I was wrong and repented to Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

After ascending, my mother dreamt that the third son I aborted visited her with his wife and child. My mother was stunned, realizing he had a family.

The fourth had extremely heavy resentment. I was ignorant and aborted him when he was two months old. In July, I once heard a baby crying in a dream. Before encountering the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I sought help to ascend with the children. The person helping said the leader was the first child, a son who resented me deeply. He brought the other three to torment me, causing everything to go wrong and bringing bad luck. Indeed, I was unlucky for many years. Not practicing Buddhism then, I only accepted my fate, enduring great suffering and misfortune. This was the karmic retribution, the cause and effect. As Buddha and Bodhisattvas, and Master Lu have enlightened us that nothing can be taken with you except your karma. No matter how long it passes, the karma will manifest when the conditions are met.

At the beginning, when I started practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, my child was naughty and hyperactive. I recited the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* to dissolve the karmic conflicts with him. One night, I dreamt the aborted son saying, "Mom, reciting the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* for me is useless." He pointed upwards, saying, "I cannot go up." I was stunned, realizing the child's naughtiness during the day was related to the aborted children. They knew I was reciting the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots*. I woke up, realizing how ignorant and foolish I had been without seeing it myself.

During the ascending process, there were often loud noises from the air conditioner, kitchen sink, refrigerator, and lights, feeling if they were jumping and running around.

The 1,000 Little Houses I vowed to recite could not be completed quickly, and the aborted children were anxious. Whenever they

were anxious, my son would suffer, becoming naughty and causing me to lose my temper. It is so pitiful to see how much suffering comes from not knowing the Dharma.

I dreamt one of the aborted sons was about to reincarnate. He came to my arms, saying he was reluctant to leave me. I gently said, "Go, live a good life." Then I saw him reincarnate into my ex-boyfriend's family. I woke up.

After completing the ascent of all six children, the biggest change was definitely in my son. He used to be very isolated, with strange expressions, thoughts, and actions, unimaginable before. Now, once he starts talking, he does not stop.

My mother often used to get angry without reason, and so did I. Now, it is completely improved. The Dharma is boundless.

Fortunately, we found Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu. Our family of three generations practices the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door diligently and will never give up. I have made a great vow: In this life and forever, I will follow the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and my benevolent Master Jun Hong Lu to practice Buddhism, propagate the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, and save sentient beings without stopping or changing.

If people do not suffer, they will not seek the path to liberation. Because of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, we know we are loved and cared for by the Buddha, Guan Yin Bodhisattva, the Dharma Protectors, and our benevolent Master Jun Hong Lu. Every day, bathed in Buddha's light, our life is so happy and beautiful. Thinking of Master Lu's smiling appearance in my dreams, we feel fatherly love and are so reassured and stable. In life, whenever we encounter any difficulties, suffering, or calamities, as long as we recite the name of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, She will hear us. Such great and immense support cannot be described with mere human words.

I, not my fellow Buddhist practitioners, will be responsible for my own karma!

Buddhist practitioner: S135

Comments: Buddhism teaches that attaining a human birth is extremely rare, and encountering the Dharma is even more so. Some spirits have waited over a thousand years for the opportunity to be reborn. If they are aborted before birth, one can only imagine the depth of their resentment and hatred. This is why some spirits are especially difficult to ascend and require many Little Houses for successful ascension. In addition to Little Houses, sincere repentance is also essential.

Case 5. An OB-GYN's journey from infertility to motherhood: Repentance, faith, and the blessing of the Bodhisattva

My husband and I got married in October 2010. Although we never used contraception, due to our demanding work schedules and my frequent colds, aches, and pains, we did not notice that several years had passed without pregnancy. As I watched people

around me getting pregnant and giving birth one after another, and with myself entering my thirties, I gradually began to feel anxious.

Being an OB-GYN myself, monthly ultrasound monitoring of my follicles was convenient, but still, nothing happened. I tried ovulation-inducing injections several times, to no avail. My husband and I then underwent a comprehensive infertility workup, and nearly all indicators came back normal. The only suspicious issue was my primary dysmenorrhea. My CA-125 levels were slightly elevated (though still within the normal range), and a gynecological exam suggested possible endometriosis. Several senior doctors consulted and recommended a laparoscopy. Could I really be a patient with primary infertility? It was difficult to accept. Sometimes, when I think about it, tears fall uncontrollably. I could not understand what karmic debt I had incurred to deserve this.

Although my family never pressured me, every time my period came, I wanted to run away and hide. I even talked about divorce multiple times, but my husband always comforted me. The more he treated me well, the more I wanted to leave. I felt that a woman who could not bear children should not hold someone else back.

Master Jun Hong Lu once enlightened us that, "There is no right or wrong in this world, only cause and effect." That is so true. After graduating, I worked in a local hospital, mainly in the obstetrics department. I experienced the joy of welcoming a new life every day. At that time, very few abortions were done in gynecology, so even working night shifts frequently, I did not feel tired, and I rarely got sick.

After a few years, I changed jobs and began performing many abortions and induced labor procedures. Again and again, I scraped out bloody gestational sacs and early human-shaped fetuses, and some of them were dismembered with ovum forceps. It was utterly heartbreaking. Even now, my heart trembles, and I can barely write about it. It was so cruel.

Abortion is the most brutal act in the human world. I deeply regret participating in those procedures (this is my personal reflection and not a criticism of OB-GYN doctors in general).

As time passed, abortion procedures became a daily occurrence at the clinic. Although I had not yet encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I increasingly felt repulsed by these operations. I grew uneasy inside. Thinking about my own infertility, I would often persuade patients not to go through with their abortions: "You are spending money only to hurt your body. The child has come to you for a reason... they are innocent."

During this period, I suffered from persistent minor ailments: colds, fever, chills, back pain, and joint pain. Even my silver bracelet inexplicably turned black. I developed gynecological issues: recurrent vaginal infections, urinary tract infections, and painful urethral abscesses. All are unusual considering how much attention I paid to hygiene. Looking back now, I believe the heavy karmic burden of killing brought Yin energy upon me.

As a child, I used to catch and eat cicada larvae with friends during summer breaks, either frying or roasting them over the

fire. The cicadas would curl up in extreme pain. Since my first menstruation, I have suffered severe dysmenorrhea. I curled up on the bed in agony, clutching my stomach. It was excruciating. Isn't that a reflection of how those cicadas were burned? This is karma. Killing does indeed harm health and fortune. That is absolutely true.

An older colleague who knew of my struggles advised me to recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* (大悲咒). She said her own skin condition had improved through chanting it. I remembered once receiving a small booklet from a temple that contained this mantra. I found it and started chanting. At first, it felt like some kind of mysterious code. After a few repetitions, I began to feel heat rising in my body. I thought it was just the weather, but it was already October.

On December 7, 2013, while searching online for ways to conceive, I unexpectedly came across words like "Master Lu," "Little House," and "infertility experience." One Buddhist practitioner had even left a QQ number (an instant messaging software service and web portal). I messaged her, asking if she was Master Lu. She said she was His disciple and asked how she could help. I told her about my infertility, and she sent me links to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door website and the Buddhist scriptures. Her warmth and kindness moved me deeply. Reading shared experiences online, I truly felt saved. Like a lost child, I had finally found a home. That is how I began doing daily recitations and reciting Little House. My husband helped me get oil lamps and incense to honour the Bodhisattvas. Soon, a simple Buddhist altar was set up at home.

The first time I offered incense, the ash curled, and the oil lamp formed a lotus-shaped wick. They are such auspicious signs! I had never seen anything like it, just as Master Lu described. This greatly boosted my faith in practicing Buddhism. I started making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and releasing captive animals. Gradually, my health improved, and my mood lightened. I no longer felt so irritable or depressed. I began tracing problems back to their karmic roots, and my resentment faded. Even my husband noticed the change and became supportive. He, too, came to believe in Buddhism.

After I began reciting Little Houses for my karmic creditors, I had several dreams of classmates taking away their children. These were the ones I had once performed abortions on. In another dream, a mid-sized bus full of happy children was driven away by a teacher. I even transformed my mother and siblings to practice Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. My mother's severe varicose veins improved significantly.

Although I still was not pregnant after several months of practice, my faith remained unshaken. I firmly believed in the Bodhisattvas and Master Lu. Just as Master Lu said, "Bodhisattvas do not interfere with your cause and effect. If you are ill, sometimes Bodhisattvas can guide you to a good doctor."

Perhaps my karmic conditions were ripening. In the second month after we prayed for a child at Putuo Mountain, I accidentally discovered I was pregnant! Sadly, due to my own negligence, it resulted in a chemical pregnancy. Though we were heartbroken, we

were also comforted. It proved I could conceive naturally. I knew my heavy karmic obstacles had caused the pregnancy to fail, but I still trusted in Buddhism, determined to keep reciting and believing that Guan Yin Bodhisattva would save me.

A few days after the miscarriage, a fellow townsman suggested I see a well-known local infertility doctor. Friends had also recommended him before, but I had never gone because the appointments required booking three months in advance and were expensive. This time, they told me the doctor also saw patients elsewhere, and I was able to book an appointment that same day for just 20 CNY. I started taking Chinese medicine regularly.

One month later, I found out I was pregnant again. This time, my urine HCG test was weakly positive, so I did not dare to be careless. I got blood tests immediately and took progesterone injections until the third month. I also took Chinese herbal medicine until the fourth month. Additionally, almost every visit to the pharmacy, I found a ride.

Despite severe morning sickness and constant vomiting, I endured bitter herbs, fatigue, and weakness. However, I was unable to recite many Little Houses. Thankfully, my mother helped me recite hundreds. My husband also releases captive animals every week. During the pregnancy, I often dreamed of a kind elderly woman giving me injections. I truly believe it was Guan Yin Bodhisattva manifesting to bless me and the baby.

Aside from routine checkups, I rested at home during the pregnancy, listening to Master Lu's radio programs and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms* aloud to my baby. In late pregnancy, while walking outside, people asked if I was carrying twins. They were shocked to learn I had such strong reactions yet remained mostly vegetarian and had no stretch marks. In contrast, babies born from rich diets of meat did not seem as big. As my due date arrived, the baby showed no signs of coming, so I was admitted to the hospital two days later as a precaution. I played the *Great Compassion Mantra* beside my bed every night, and I even heard it faintly in my sleep.

After two days without progress, the hospital tried several labor-inducing methods, but none worked. My husband and I grew anxious, but I firmly believed in Bodhisattva's arrangement. On June 4, I underwent a cesarean section while chanting the *Great Compassion Mantra*. At the sound of her first loud cry, my daughter was born. She is 4.2 kilograms (the ultrasound had predicted 3.5+), clean and beautiful. Her bright eyes gazed at me. Lying on the operating table, tears of joy streamed down my face. I was finally a mother.

After surgery, the doctor told me the baby was so large that natural delivery might have failed, possibly leading to hours of pain before a cesarean was needed anyway. My low-lying placenta also posed a high bleeding risk. None of which the ultrasound could have predicted. No wonder labor never started. Bodhisattva knew that a natural birth could endanger both of us, so I was not given the opportunity. Guan Yin Bodhisattva once again saved our lives. I am deeply grateful.

Let me share another Dharma-joyful experience. Last year, Buddhist Practitioner C gifted me a *Buddhism in Plain Terms* book that included a photo of Master Lu in a white shirt. It reminded me of a strange, unforgettable dream I had ten years ago in my sophomore year. I dreamed of a professor in a white shirt and black suit giving a lecture from a podium. I knelt and said, "Thank you, Master, for saving my life." At the time, I thought it was funny and even told my family. Looking back, that professor was exactly how Master Lu looks during Dharma talks.

The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door made me a mother, saved my marriage, and gave my life new meaning.

I made a vow before the Bodhisattva that I would never again perform surgery on abortions. I will forever follow Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu in practicing the Dharma. I am truly grateful that Buddhism gave me a new life, helped me understand karma, and confirmed the truth of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. As long as we cultivate sincerely and apply the Three Golden Buddhist Practices, Bodhisattvas will surely save us.

Dharma Practitioner: N136

Comments: The curling of incense ash or the formation of a lotus in the oil lamp wick is an auspicious sign, indicating that the Bodhisattva or Dharma Protectors have come to offer their blessings. For reference images, please see our previous publications [8].

Discussion

This study examines the spiritual and karmic consequences of abortion, miscarried fetuses, or deceased fertilized embryos through the lens of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, drawing on Buddhist teachings and real-life case studies. While abortion is frequently debated as a medical or ethical issue, this discussion emphasizes a third dimension of spiritual and karmic repercussions, which may provide critical insights into the persistent physical, emotional, and interpersonal challenges faced by individuals and families post-abortion.

According to Master Lu, the spirits of aborted, miscarried fetuses, or deceased fertilized embryos do not simply vanish but remain connected to the mother or family, manifesting as health issues, infertility, psychological disorders, or family discord. Case studies in this paper support these teachings. For example, Case 1 describes a dream encounter with a miscarried child that prompted spiritual resolution, while Case 2 illustrates how reciting Buddhist scriptures and using "Little Houses" alleviated marital strife and improved a child's behaviour and academic performance.

These cases and our previous studies suggest a truth: spirits of abortion may contribute to chronic or unexplained illnesses, ranging from gynaecological conditions to psychiatric disorders [8-23]. Documented examples, including gastric cancer, autism, infertility, and family breakdowns, reinforce the idea that abortion-related karmic debts can profoundly influence one's life trajectory. Notably, Master Lu attributes one cause of autism in some children to the presence of vengeful aborted spirits [18], offering a spiritual explanation for conditions often considered medically inexplicable.

The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door provides remedies for addressing these spiritual consequences. Practices such as reciting the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* and Little Houses, making vows, and performing life liberation facilitate healing and karmic resolution. However, the efficacy of these practices hinges on sincere repentance and awareness of karmic responsibility. Case studies emphasize that the quantity of recitations alone is insufficient without genuine remorse.

This study also highlights the transgenerational impact of abortion-related karma. Descendants of those who have undergone or performed abortions may experience inexplicable illnesses or disabilities, as seen in Case 2 and other anecdotes [15, 16, 18]. These findings challenge conventional medical and psychological frameworks and invite interdisciplinary dialogue between Dharma practices and health sciences.

Given the potential link between abortion and chronic health issues, we urge researchers to investigate these associations rigorously. Large-scale studies involving millions of participants could explore the relationship between abortion and health outcomes, including gynaecological conditions, psychological disorders, and behavioural changes in children and grandchildren.

To ensure study validity, control groups must exclude individuals with histories of contraceptive pill use, IVF, or irregular menstruation, as these may involve spiritual harm according to Master Lu's teachings. Fertilized embryos, even in IVF or spontaneous miscarriages, are considered to house spirits, and their loss constitutes a form of abortion in spiritual terms. Comprehensive data collection should prioritize physical, emotional, and behavioural outcomes across generations.

Emerging research has identified associations between abortion and adverse outcomes. For instance, induced abortion is linked to an increased long-term risk of mental health-related hospitalization [3], while pregnancy loss, particularly miscarriage, is associated with depressive mood and suicidal behaviour, especially among adolescent girls [51]. However, these studies, which focus solely on physical and psychological dimensions, remain incomplete without considering spiritual perspectives. Integrating spiritual insights could provide a more comprehensive understanding of abortion's broader impacts, fostering healthier and more harmonious families and communities.

Master Lu enlightened us: "There is no medicine for regret in this world. Everything is already gone when we begin to regret. However, for a Buddhist practitioner, there is a cure for regret-reciting the *Eighty-eight Buddhas Great Repentance*." OB-GYNs who perform abortion procedures may develop leukemia as karmic retribution [8]. Case 5 also shows that such actions can lead to infertility. Master Lu's blog has further reported a case that it may cause breast cancer and lung cancer. This illustrates the severe consequences of killing karma. Fortunately, they ultimately found liberation through the "regret medicine," which helped them regain their health. Similarly, women who have undergone abortions or engaged in any actions that result in the death of fertilized eggs

can not only restore their health through Buddhist practice but also resolve their karmic debts. In doing so, they can avoid being dragged by karmic forces into the Three Evil Realms in their next life.

In our previous report, we discussed the well-being of medical doctors and highlighted the issue of doctors bearing the karmic burden of their patients [17]. Case 5 vividly illustrates this assertion. The contrast in her health before and after performing abortion surgeries is striking. As explained in Q&A 1, the spirit of the aborted baby, having nowhere to go, may attach itself to the mother, siblings, or the OB-GYN who performed the procedure. Therefore, designing a study on this issue is straightforward: simply examine the health changes in OB-GYNs before and after they begin performing abortions.

In the human world, prisons confine criminals; in the underworld, hells detain sinful spirits; and in the heavens, celestial prisons hold wrongdoers. While human prisons and underworld hells share some standards of judgment, they also differ significantly. For instance, killing animals may not break human laws, but violates underworld laws. Breaking human laws leads to punishment in this world, just as violating underworld laws brings consequences in the spiritual realm. Understanding human law helps us live well in this life, while embracing Dharma guides us to live virtuously in both the human and spiritual worlds, now and in future lives.

In Buddhism, the ten bad deeds are: killing, stealing, sexual misconduct, greed, hatred, ignorance, lying, loose speech, harsh speech, and divisive speech. The ten good deeds are simply the opposite of these. The Buddha encouraged cultivating these good deeds. Whether one chooses to follow the path of good or bad deeds is a personal decision. Performing abortions as an OB-GYN is a legally recognized profession in many regions, driven by societal needs, though it is prohibited in others. From a secular perspective, this work is neither inherently right nor wrong. However, from a karmic perspective, it carries consequences. Positive actions yield positive outcomes, while negative actions lead to negative retribution.

Those who understand only worldly knowledge, without studying the Dharma, may unknowingly sow seeds of negative karma. By the time the consequences arise, regret may come too late. Therefore, doctors should study the Dharma to protect themselves wisely. Pregnant women should study the Dharma to make wise choices. In truth, everyone should study Dharma to cultivate positive karma and avoid negative karma.

The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door offers hope, emphasizing that no karmic obstacle is insurmountable. Through dedicated Buddhist practice, individuals have reported transformative improvements in their spiritual, physical, emotional, and social well-being.

Abortion transcends its medical framework, engaging complex moral, ethical, religious, and political dimensions. Rooted in a deep concern for human well-being, this article reflects the compassionate salvation offered by Buddhas and Bodhisattvas to

those with an affinity for Buddhist teachings. The Dharma is non-coercive, gently inviting individuals to explore its wisdom while respecting the choice of others to remain distant. Using these teachings to judge or harm others contradicts the core principles of Dharma and the boundless compassion of Bodhisattvas.

Conclusion

Abortion, miscarriage, and the loss of fertilized embryos extend far beyond observable medical effects, carrying profound spiritual and karmic consequences. Through the lens of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, this study integrates Buddhist teachings with real-life testimonies to illuminate these spiritual impacts and proposes practical Buddhist practices for resolution. While further interdisciplinary research is needed to explore these spiritual mechanisms within clinical and social frameworks, the documented experiences highlight the transformative power of sincere repentance and Dharma practice.

For those contemplating abortion, we compassionately encourage deep reflection on its enduring spiritual implications and respectfully advise against proceeding. For those who have experienced abortion, miscarriage, or the loss of fertilized embryos, genuine repentance and dedicated efforts to guide the spirit's ascension can effectively resolve karmic burdens, fostering peace, healing, and renewal for individuals and their families.

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Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the patients. All the experimental procedures and practices by the presenters were done by themselves independently.

Statement by Translator and Writer

The 27 Q&As and 5 cases in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

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The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioner may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as

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